

THE STUDENTS' WRITING PERFORMANCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: EMPIRICAL STUDY IN ENGLISH CREATIVE WRITING CLASS

SITI MARIA ULFA

Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra, Pascasarjana Universitas Negeri Surabaya, Surabaya; Indonesia.
Email: siti.17070956003@mhs.unesa.ac.id

SUSANTO

Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra, Pascasarjana Universitas Negeri Surabaya, Surabaya; Indonesia.
Email: susanto@unesa.ac.id

OIKUREMAPURWATI

Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra, Pascasarjana Universitas Negeri Surabaya, Surabaya; Indonesia.
Email: oikuremapurwati@unesa.ac.id

Abstract

This study investigates students' writing performance regarding the problem that obstruct their perception of good writing skills. It also examines students' ability to identify their composition, including their introductory paragraph, supporting sentences, concluding paragraph, supporting sentences, concluding paragraph, and correct linguistic errors such as spelling, grammar, punctuation, etc. Using a qualitative method, data were collected from undergraduate students who enrolled in a creative writing class. The participants were 13 students aged 20-21 years and were interviewed to learn about the tools and tactics to improve their writing's linguistic accuracy. The findings revealed that most of the pupils' issues were related to language use. Mastering a second language is a different issue in that they must learn the grammar, vocabularies, syntactic structures, and other aspects of the new language. Students who had difficulty reading and writing in English had to work harder to develop with concepts and thoughts for their writing assignments.

Keywords: Creative writing, performance, undergraduate, higher education, English language

1. Introduction

Writing may be defined as a process of communication in which numerous ideas and someone's feelings come together in written form. Effective writing is critical, and it becomes more critical as communicative language instruction principles (Uludag et al., 2019). Compared to the other three abilities to listen, read, and speak, writing is frequently seen as the most complex, making it a difficult skill for most EFL learners (Torrance, 2000). This is because writing is a skill that must be learned and taught and cannot be acquired spontaneously (Naghdi-pour & Kadhim, 2021). Moreover, teaching writing in English requires careful planning because writing skills are not automatically accepted by second language learners (Cahyono et al., 2016); thus, writing is placed at the final stage of language development within the theory of second language acquisition (D. Ferris & Eckstein, 2020). Additionally, conveying thoughts and emotions through writing is a complex process. When students are required to write, they must consider three critical elements: the subject, the goal,

and the audience (Torrance, 2000). The subject denotes the issue being discussed, the goal denotes that text's function (whether intended to provide an example, explain, or debate), and the audience suggests the intended readers. In other words, to write an adequate composition, students must possess sufficient knowledge of these three components.

Furthermore, it is critical to remember that writing is distinct from other skills. Writing is not a skill that a man acquires spontaneously like speaking is. It is a taught behavior that is culturally specific (Kimb et al., n.d.). In one's hand, it is considered that writing requires various abilities and conventions, including writing readiness and knowledge of grammatical rules, for pupils to develop into proficient and successful writers. On the other hand, those may become an issue that may arise during writing instruction and learning in the classroom. Moreover, teacher frequently focuses exclusively on the product of these students' writing, without exerting any pressure or intention or providing constructive feedback on their process of producing such an excellent composition in writing, because writing is more than simply putting pen to paper or writing down ideas; it is also about how these ideas are presented and expressed effectively (Nik et al., 2010). As it turns out, as long as students complete the assignment on time, the teacher does not provide such constructive feedback on their writing. When a teacher provides critical feedback, it is not always beneficial to the pupils because they cannot rearrange their writing. It is essential to look up what is happening around the writing class again; it is also critical to look deeper at how the writing class should be conducted to match the expectations.

Writing requires several skills and conventions like the organization to develop ideas and information (Wright et al., 2021). Furthermore, the accuracy in choosing the correct words to avoid ambiguity and the right use of grammatical order is a subject matter in writing. Students need to have a lot of practice in writing, such as writing a diary every day, and practicing all day long (Putri & Salatar, 2015). However, it is scarce in EFL contexts that undergraduate students spend more time attending to language-related issues in their written work due to insufficient exposure to linguistic input and sources of scaffolding or feedback (Naghdipour & Kadhim, 2021). Hence, this study examines some of the factors affecting students writing performance and problematic areas i.e., spelling, grammar and punctuation. It also explores the likely resources or strategies students consult to detect and fix linguistic errors in writing. It is hoped that the finding informs teachers and EFL in similar contexts to design more effective pedagogical spaces that offer students opportunities to engage in various learning and feedback resources and strategies to better opportunities linguistic issues in their writing.

1.1 Conceptual or theoretical framework

Writing pedagogy has evolved significantly in the second half of the twentieth century, transitioning from product-based to process-based instruction, genre-based instruction, eclectic approaches, and writing across the curriculum, to name a few, resulting in a spectrum of instructional strategies ranging from those emphasizing form to those emphasizing meaning. In recent decades, the shift away from purely linguistic product-based approaches to writing instruction is best reflected in the learning-to-write (Knoch et al., 2015). writing-to-

learn dichotomy, with the latter receiving increased attention as writing gains broader recognition in knowledge construction and sharing across disciplines. While most research on accuracy development in writing classes and programs has focused on corrective feedback practices, engaging students in disciplinary content has been suggested to scaffold their written linguistic accuracy development and build their social literature repertoire. However, research on the impact of disciplinary acculturation via writing-to-learn perspectives in assisting students in improving their linguistic accuracy in writing is still in its infancy (D. R. Ferris et al., 2013).

Most research on the development of linguistic correctness in L2 writing classes focuses on written corrective feedback (WCF) or grammar correction, as any WCF intervention aims to promote linguistic accuracy. Advocates of corrective theories for pupils' writing target linguistic difficulties or faults. Among them is the noticing hypothesis (Schmidt, 2001), which believes that negative evidence or incorrect instances of the target language are necessary for learning. WCF can focus language learners' attention on form in the context of a communicative act as a form-focused pedagogical intervention. When learners examine and reflect on the feedback or input they have received, they have the opportunity to identify gaps in their inter language and take action to close them through the use of mediating learning tools and resources. While providing feedback on writers' faults is vital for writing improvement, it is insufficient. The output hypothesis credits students' engagement with input, arguing that language learners need opportunities to communicate with others in the target language to test their ideas or identify gaps in their linguistic knowledge. It is considered that when students become aware of deficiencies in their inter language, they progress from fluency to linguistic accuracy and may change or fill in the gaps in their language knowledge. Similarly, skill acquisition theory advocates for including corrective feedback methods in second language writing workshops. According to this hypothesis, the practice of correcting errors and bridging gaps in learner interlanguage might result in increased language automatization. In other words, students spend sufficient time practicing various aspects of the target language that their explicit knowledge becomes implicit or consolidated.

1.2 purpose of the study

The problems of this research are formulated as follows: (1) to what extent can students in higher education identify and to fix their written linguistic errors? (2) What strategies and resources do EFL students in higher education fix their written linguistic errors?

2. Method

2.1 Types of research

This study employs a descriptive research methodology. The methodology section discusses the setting, the subjects, the study's design, the research instruments, and the procedure. The data in this study are in the form of written records due to their relevance to students' essays, such as their organization and language; nonetheless, the data source was the written English class students. It is crucial to dig further into the phrase "data" and "source of data," which

are essential components of any research required to address the issues addressed in this study.

2.2 Setting and research subject

The participants were students enrolled in the fifth semester and joined an English creating writing class and the age ranged between 20 and 21 years old in STKIP PGRI Bangkalan, Madura Island, and East Java Province, Indonesia.

2.3 Data collection technique

Students were instructed to carefully read their writings and detect and correct possible linguistic faults in spelling, grammar, and punctuation, which are the most familiar parts of linguistic accuracy. The students and teachers were interviewed to see their expressions on their works to answer another research question. The questions mainly focused on the writing tasks and projects students encountered, feedback received, and strategies used to reduce linguistic errors in writing.

2.4 Data analysis technique

In this research, the data analysis technique was done manually by counting the spelling, grammar, and punctuation errors students identified and fixed. The interviews data from participants were transcribed and filed. The scripts were subjected to thematic analysis to determine the recurring themes and patterns and figure out their interrelationships.

3. Results and Discussion

The first part discusses students' composition, including their introductory paragraph, supporting sentences, concluding paragraph, and correct linguistic errors such as spelling, grammar, punctuation, etc. Students were asked to write an essay of a topic of a person they adore much. These tables below show particular samples of the students' composition in their spelling, grammar, and others.

Table 1: Extracts on error correction attempts from students' composition

Error attempt	Example
Spelling	Original:...she will do her best to her familly*...
	Edited:...she will do her best to her family...
Grammar	Original: She does not fake smiles...
	Edited: Her smile is not fake...
Punctuation	Original:...my mother is that she is naturally*, friendly welcoming...
	Edited:...my mother is that she is naturally friendly welcoming...

Besides, the students' composition is also discussed here and table 2 presents the samples of their parts of the composition, namely the introductory paragraph, supporting sentences, and concluding paragraph. An introductory paragraph contains a thesis statement that introduces

the essay's main idea. The functions of a thesis statement are to state precisely the topic of the essay, to list the subtopics of the main topic, to mention the method of the organization and the location of the thesis statement itself, usually at the end of the introductory paragraph (Alice Oshima & Ann Hogue, 1996).

Thesis statement is a statement that instructs the reader on how to view the meaning of the topic at hand. It is also called a road map; it tells the readers what to expect from the rest of the text. A thesis statement is usually a single sentence near the beginning, but often it is at the end of the first paragraph that presents arguments to the readers. As seen below, thesis statements are written by subjects.

Table2: Students' Original Essay Taken from Students' Account

Introductory paragraph	My idol and my role model is Iqbaal Dhiafakhri Ramadan. He is an actor and singer from Jakarta
Supporting sentences	...when he was in the 2 nd grade of middle school, iqbaal left his boy band because at that time he got a scholarship at UWC Amarica, he preferred to continue his education rather than his career even though at that time his career could be said as a successful career. After 2 years in America, he returned to Indonesia and returned to the world of entertainment after a vacuum of several years
Concluding Paragraph	...for iqbaal thank you for being an idol who provides a good example for his fans. I Love you... ...I like her because she can do anything in her young. She can inspire many people espically the woman I want to be like her because she can build her busissnes without her parent's help help but she makes her parents pround of her. And she said that her biggest inspiration is her parents and it same as me...

In some essays written by the subjects, a concise introductory paragraph which does not expose the readers to much information can lead them to predict what the essay is about is found. As shown in the example below, the essay talks about an idol. Another student wrote a short description of someone in their life. This is the introduction that may introduce what the writer wants actually to share. It is a concise and clear sentence. Since it is descriptive essay, the first to come up is dealing with the introduction of the person discussed. And the writer wants to describe his mom as role model in his life. It suits the term of leading readers to what is the essay going to say. Mentioning the person's name that will be discussed is another exciting part of this introduction because the reader pays attention carefully to the name itself.

One of student wrote a complete sentence In the part of introduction because it mentions the name of the figure that the writer likes. The writer tries to introduce who she adores by saying the family member of Putri Tanjung. But it can be assumed that not everyone knows who Chairul Tanjung is, even his daughter, namely Putri Tanjung. What the writer should propose is adding additional information about it. The teacher also asked the students to compose

another topic of writing. It was recount text; telling a phenomenon or experience, they have ever had in their life. The introduction of the essay is complete enough since it has several sentences and a thesis statement.

In one of essay shows a good starting point by mentioning exact time the story happened and the other feeling that the writer felt at that time. Then, it is also still in the introduction part of the essay, and the thesis statement was there. The writers mentioned the specific activity in this part where he met his idol, a football player. It is very usual, but the writer tries to inform the reader with his main idea or topic sentence of the essay. This essay is mainly started with a straight topic sentence which is relatively short and very general. It is not a good introduction; the point is in 'I got a lot moments'. It is clear that readers only be given moments without knowing whether the moments are entertaining or not.

One example below indicates a different case from previous model. This is the first part of the introduction. From several sentences, one sentence refers to the main idea. However, If the writer has written down the word 'fun moments', it is better for him to enclose what moment is this. It is better to be done since it raises the reader's interest to come closer to the essay. We figure maybe there is a reason the writer did not put the 'moment' itself. Another confusing essay that the students wrote was there is no introduction in this essay. Another essay subject that the students should compose is a kind of an argumentative essay. The students are given a free topic to arrange based on the topic they most like. It is interesting to look at the result and can have the patterns of their essays.

Another essay shows the first part of the essay which is initiated by mentioning her hobby. The writer focuses on one hobby to be discussed in her essay, listening to music. In her first paragraph, in terms of the introduction, she mentions one reason why she like that hobby, listening to music. Music can make her feel comfortable. Hence, the thesis statement exists at the end of the paragraph. It is similar with this example below since the essay talks about student roles on campus in an argumentative essay. It should be highlighted that there should be at least one main idea od topic sentence in the introductory paragraph.

The concluding paragraph is another critical component of an essay since it reminds the reader of the essay's thesis statement. The concluding sentence informs the reader that the paragraph is complete and concludes the development of the paragraph's subject. The writer wrapped the essay first for the two-concluding paragraph in the first example. This is what we call an excellent paragraph since it wrapped up the important point and again the writer reminds the main idea by using other words but still in similar issues. Knowing the students' productions by students above, it can be said because writing is more intricate and abstract than speech (Chen & Zhang, 2019). Students need to have more practice because sometimes wiring could torment for students. Writing requires many skills and conventions specifically writing readiness and grammatical rules. Besides, teachers also face significant challenges when they teach this kind of skill since writing is putting pen to paper to write down ideas and how the ideas are presented and expressed effectively. To begin, writing is a cognitive process. It is a difficult skill to master. It is drafted, revised, and edited over an extended period. Students and instructors should work and cooperate to reach a satisfactory writing

proficiency level. Thus, one of studies proposed that writing teachers focus on the process of writing rather than the final product(Lan et al., 2019).

From interviews result revealed that the students need lecturers to carefully choose tasks which require students to concentrate on the writing and editing processes. This involves allowing them time to work on a paper, time to collaborate with colleagues while also working independently, time to deal with the content, organization, and, eventually, the proofreading stage (Myhill et al., 2013). This is the thinking process that results in other people making discoveries. In other words, students can develop their writing abilities if professors encourage them to write often. Hence, it has been asserted that great teachers write and engage their students in their writing processes and outputs (Benetos& Bétrancourt, 2020). In their study, the direct experience with the assignments teachers assign to their students shows the students acquire a better sensitivity to the writing issues pupils face(Hajar et al., 2021). Thus, teachers should initiate their writing, as writing implies exchanging and discovering new ideas, which helps both parties. Then, it is emphasized that "there is no set of criteria that can 'transform education' unless teachers cherish and challenge the human heart, which is at the center of good teaching". In other words, teachers should actively listen to and stimulate the students, and share their viewpoints and ideas with them, to become more receptive and accepting of them in the long run(Li & Casanave, 2012)(Lestari et al., 2021).

In addition, when students write, they should be taught to think critically and creatively(Zhang & Hyland, 2018). They assert that a smart writer thinks critically throughout the writing process. They continue, "No combination of writing ideas and strategies can ever help you write carefully if you lack critical thinking." As a result, teachers should encourage and create opportunities for students to be adventurous with the language, venture beyond what they have learned, and experiment with the impacts of writing. This helps our kids engage with a new language; the effort to articulate new concepts and the constant use of their hands and minds creates a unique "process" for reinforcing learning. Because writing and thinking are inextricably linked, writing is an indispensable component of any language study (Lim & Polio, 2020).

Thus, lecturers should learn not to take themselves too seriously when writing. Lecturers can periodically remind your students that "it is not a sin to toss away an entire writing page if it is simply not functioning (not correct)". As a result, both lecturers and students will gain a sense of fulfillment and comprehension from the exchanging of new ideas. Also, there is a generally held assumption that a student must read extensively to be successful writer. This is often true because reading enables students to develop competency (Li & Casanave, 2012). According to the Indonesian Ministry of Education, reading and writing are interrelated processes like speaking and listening. This demonstrates the connection between reading and writing, as readers generate meaning from the books they read, whereas writers construct meaning from the writings they write. Students and teachers alike must read extensively to develop, construct, and organize ideas to write competently and effectively.

Besides, children who read extensively can employ various linguistic skills while formulating their ideas and thoughts and putting them on paper. Our greatest desire is that professors will promote extensive reading among students. Though it is not simple to cultivate and sustain students' enthusiasm for reading, lecturers should begin by effectively fulfilling their roles as motivators, as it is stated by (Yu & Hu, 2017). By including newspapers, magazines, and other reading materials in our lectures, we can instill a reading habit in our children. As a result, pupils who read widely will develop into more proficient and successful writers. Moreover, instructors should educate students about how and why they write and encourage them to write freely, eloquently, and effectively and assess correctly (Zheng & Yu, 2019) which can use either holistic or analytical (Rezaei & Lovorn, 2010). That is why giving the task to students should be meaningful, relevant and realistic tasks (Tok & Kandemir, 2015). In addition, one of a study also proposed that students should understand the value of writing as a tool for learning and communicating (Mahfoodh, 2017). Writing is a critical learning tool for children because it enables them to experience or go through the "thinking process" or "writing process," which consists of three stages: pre-writing (brainstorming), writing and rewriting (revising), and lastly editing (proof reading).

The importance of writing which comes from the students' own ability to acquire language skills namely fluency, correctness, and the appropriateness of meanings and messages, as writing is a critical too for students in learning and communicating. As a result, writing is a significant mode of assessment across our educational system. The majority of examinations and assessments evaluate written performance. Thus, writing abilities are critical for students to develop and perfect because they are assessed based on their writing (Mao & Crosthwaite, 2019). Nonetheless, the primary reason children should develop strong writing abilities is to use them creatively to connect effectively with others and the world around them. As a result, teachers and students should work closely together to reach the minimum level of writing proficiency demanded of our students. We believe that lecturers should be aware of their students' diverse requirements and desires. As a result, teachers must evaluate and reflect on their approach to writing instruction. Additionally, teachers may choose to enroll in or register for a "refresher course" or a "professional development course" to stay current and fulfil our students' unique requirements and demands today.

Like any other skill, developing writing skills takes a lot of practice and feedback to become automatic, just like any other skill (Parr & Timperley, 2010). There were also not a lot of well-organized efforts, like strategy instruction and training, to help students keep working on their linguistic accuracy in this setting. Other than in a few cases where disciplinary faculty stressed the importance of linguistic accuracy by, for example, underlining some selected errors, students were on their own to correct linguistic errors in their writing. Even though they did not get enough help from their teachers, students used many resources and strategies (Flores-Ferrés et al., 2020); (Plakans et al., 2019) to fix linguistic mistakes in their writing. Many students proofread or edit their written work to better prepare for exams or impress teachers for better grades. They were mainly motivated by personal goals, career plans, and access to many online learning resources. Even though there is a lot of evidence that corrective feedback can help students improve their linguistic accuracy in writing (Zhao,

2010), some teachers might have been put off by low expectations from their institutions and practical constraints like a lot of teaching and not enough training (Naghdi-pour & Kadhim, 2021). They might also think that giving feedback on language-related issues is not their job.

Hence, students' attitudes about what should be important changed because of their disciplinary acculturation. They thought content, expertise, or language should be more important (Koltovskaia, 2020). Also, language learning programs and disciplinary programs have different ideas and expectations about what students should learn. They also used more peer feedback and looked for technology-based tools to help them improve and correct their mistakes, which shows that this is true. Because these students have less experience with disciplinary content and are more interested in language learning skills, this could be a reason for the difference.

4. Conclusion

According to the findings of this study, significant exposure to the English language has improved the writing skills of undergraduate students. Evidence suggests that these undergraduates have learned writing abilities and have progressed to become excellent writers. It is believed that prolonged exposure and reading help develop developing strong writing abilities. Writing is difficult and time-consuming, but regular exposure to reading and writing will enhance writing skills. Overall, while the findings of this study may encourage additional discussion on second language growth in writing, they are difficult to generalize to other EFL situations due to the small sample size. On the other hand, the study has various pedagogical implications for problems where English as a medium of instruction policy has been implemented to prepare students for improved academic and professional outcomes. The findings show that providing students with error identification and repair abilities at a younger age may give them the necessary toolset to cope with language challenges later in their academic writing.

Similarly, rather than sharing rubrics and marking systems, English disciplinary department should push for more practical techniques to aiding students in revising their written work. Even if time is limited or administrative duties prevent them from doing so, faculty may seek out ways to familiarize students with alternative feedback strategies and resources to help them make better compromises between language knowledge and disciplinary knowledge whenever and wherever necessary. Teachers might, for example, encourage students to attend writing centers, learning clubs, and laboratories, as well as participate in formative assessment, to enhance their understanding of such tactics. Strategies like self-editing and peer-editing. Providing whole-class comments on the most prevalent faults after each significant student submission by constructing brief mini-lessons of 15 to 20 minutes might be another attempt to assist students in minimizing language-related errors in their writing. This might enhance students' understanding of the need to write grammatically acceptable texts in academic environments and improve the quality of their written work. However, there are limits that future research should address when researching students' written language accuracy.

References

- Alice Oshima & Ann Hogue. (1996). *Introduction to Academic Writing*, Second Edition (The Longman Academic Writing Series) | Alice Oshima, Ann Hogue, Addison Wesley Longman | download. Addison Wesley Publishing Company, 1–221.
- Benetos, K., & Bétrancourt, M. (2020). Digital authoring support for argumentative writing: What does it change? *Journal of Writing Research*, 12(1), 263–290. <https://doi.org/10.17239/JOWR-2020.12.01.09>
- Cahyono, B. Y., Mukminatien, N., & Amrina, R. (2016). Indonesian Students Writing Proficiency in Using Complex Sentence. 4(9), 22–32.
- Chen, J., & Zhang, L. J. (2019). Assessing student-writers' self-efficacy beliefs about text revision in EFL writing. *Assessing Writing*, 40(February), 27–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2019.03.002>
- Ferris, D., & Eckstein, G. (2020). Language matters: Examining the language-related needs and wants of writers in a first-year university writing course. *Journal of Writing Research*, 12(2), 321–364. <https://doi.org/10.17239/jowr-2020.12.02.02>
- Ferris, D. R., Liu, H., Sinha, A., & Senna, M. (2013). Written corrective feedback for individual L2 writers. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 22(3), 307–329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jslw.2012.09.009>
- Flores-Ferrés, M., van Weijen, D., & Rijlaarsdam, G. (2020). Teachers' Writing Practices and Contextual Features in Grades 7-12 of Chilean Public Schools. In *Journal of Writing Research* (Vol. 12, Issue 2). <https://doi.org/10.17239/jowr-2020.12.02.03>
- Hajar, I., Umanailo, M. C. B., Umanailo, R., Indriani, D. E., Handayani, N., & Nursyifa, A. (2021). The effectiveness of demonstration method in learning poetry for grade X students of SMA Negeri Sawa. *Proceedings of the 11th Annual International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management*, 6198–6208.
- Kimb, L., Hicks, A., & Weisberg, T. (n.d.). *Process Writing June 5*.
- Knoch, U., Rouhshad, A., Oon, S. P., & Storch, N. (2015). What happens to ESL students' writing after three years of study at an English medium university? *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 28, 39–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jslw.2015.02.005>
- Koltovskaia, S. (2020). Student engagement with automated written corrective feedback (AWCF) provided by Grammarly: A multiple case study. *Assessing Writing*, 44(February), 100450. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2020.100450>
- Lan, G., Liu, Q., & Staples, S. (2019). Grammatical complexity: 'What Does It Mean' and 'So What' for L2 writing classrooms? *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 46(April), 100673. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jslw.2019.100673>
- Lestari, G. D., Izzati, U. A., Adhe, K. R., & Indriani, D. E. (2021). Professional commitment: Its effect on kindergarten teachers' organizational citizenship behavior. *Cypriot Journal of Educational Sciences*, 16(4), 2037–2048. <https://doi.org/10.18844/cjes.v16i4.6072>
- Li, Y., & Casanave, C. P. (2012). Two first-year students' strategies for writing from sources: Patchwriting or plagiarism? *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 21(2), 165–180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jslw.2012.03.002>
- Lim, J., & Polio, C. (2020). Multimodal assignments in higher education: Implications for multimodal writing tasks for L2 writers. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 47(February), 100713. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jslw.2020.100713>
- Mahfoodh, O. H. A. (2017). "I feel disappointed": EFL university students' emotional responses towards teacher written feedback. *Assessing Writing*, 31, 53–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2016.07.001>

- Mao, S. S., & Crosthwaite, P. (2019). Investigating written corrective feedback: (Mis)alignment of teachers' beliefs and practice. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 45(May), 46–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jslw.2019.05.004>
- Myhill, D., Jones, S., & Watson, A. (2013). Grammar matters: How teachers' grammatical knowledge impacts on the teaching of writing. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 36, 77–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2013.07.005>
- Naghdipour, B., & Kadhim, K. A. (2021). Exploring Omani EFL students' written linguistic accuracy development in disciplinary contexts. *3L: Language, Linguistics, Literature*, 27(3), 129–144. <https://doi.org/10.17576/3L-2021-2703-08>
- Nik, Y. A., Sani, B., Chik, M. N. W., Jusoff, K., & Hasbollah, H. R. (2010). The writing performance of undergraduates in the University of Technology Mara , Terengganu , Malaysia. *Journal of Languages and Culture*, 1(April), 8–14.
- Parr, J. M., & Timperley, H. S. (2010). Feedback to writing, assessment for teaching and learning and student progress. *Assessing Writing*, 15(2), 68–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2010.05.004>
- Plakans, L., Liao, J. T., & Wang, F. (2019). “I should summarize this whole paragraph”: Shared processes of reading and writing in iterative integrated assessment tasks. *Assessing Writing*, 40(February), 14–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2019.03.003>
- Putri, F. A., & Salatar, B. (2015). Developing Students ' Writing Skill By Diary Writing Habit. The 3rd International Multidisciplinary Conference on Social Sciences (IMCoSS 2015) Bandar Lampung University (UBL), IMCoSS, 8–10.
- Rezaei, A. R., & Lovorn, M. (2010). Reliability and validity of rubrics for assessment through writing. *Assessing Writing*, 15(1), 18–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2010.01.003>
- Tok, Ş., & Kandemir, A. (2015). Effects of Creative Writing Activities on Students' Achievement in Writing, Writing Dispositions and Attitude to English. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 174, 1635–1642. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.815>
- Torrance, M. (2000). Individual differences in undergraduate essay-writing strategies: A longitudinal study. *Higher Education*, 39(2), 181–200.
- Uludag, P., Lindberg, R., McDonough, K., & Payant, C. (2019). Exploring L2 writers' source-text use in an integrated writing assessment. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 46(January), 100670. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jslw.2019.100670>
- Wright, K. L., Hodges, T. S., Enright, E., & Abbott, J. (2021). The relationship between middle and high school students' motivation to write, value of writing, writer selfbeliefs, and writing outcomes. *Journal of Writing Research*, 12(3), 601–623. <https://doi.org/10.17239/jowr-2021.12.03.03>
- Yu, S., & Hu, G. (2017). Understanding university students' peer feedback practices in EFL writing: Insights from a case study. *Assessing Writing*, 33(March), 25–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2017.03.004>
- Zhang, Z. (Victor), & Hyland, K. (2018). Student engagement with teacher and automated feedback on L2 writing. *Assessing Writing*, 36(July 2017), 90–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2018.02.004>
- Zhao, H. (2010). Investigating learners' use and understanding of peer and teacher feedback on writing: A comparative study in a Chinese English writing classroom. *Assessing Writing*, 15(1), 3–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2010.01.002>
- Zheng, Y., & Yu, S. (2019). What has been assessed in writing and how? Empirical evidence from *Assessing Writing* (2000–2018). *Assessing Writing*, 42(August), 100421. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2019.100421>